

**Between the Cracks of a Dichotomous World:
Rethinking Gendered Space**

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A whole history remains to be written of spaces — which would at the same time be the history of powers (both these terms in the plural) — from the great strategies of geopolitics to the little tactics of the habitat.

— *Michel Foucault, Of Other Spaces*

Throughout history, architecture and other types of space arrangement have reinforced status differences within the binary system of women and men. Small "tactics of the habitat" are viewed through the lens of gender. Preciado (2018) notes that when architecture seemingly innocuously serves basic natural needs, a perverse and effective policy of limiting access is established in which doors, windows, furniture, walls, partitions, exits, and entrances operate as a complex apparatus in the service of gendered mechanisms. This essay shows how the rigid categorization in gendered spaces does not include intersex and transgender people, a small and highly marginalized segment of the general population. In short, I suggest that gender is a discipline that produces bodies and identities and acts as an effective form of social control, and can be minimized through the application of gender-natural spaces.

This essay aims to give a general overview of the question of the gendered space without providing specific guidelines for every case. Prisons, bathrooms, changing rooms, outside public spaces, shelters, and other spaces that exclude one gender, have different purposes and require various security measures — so to narrow my claim, I am focusing on 'The Bathroom Problem' Browne (2004). I believe the spatial binary segregation of public bathrooms must be compromised due to its harmfulness and groundlessness. To support my position, I use the theory of performativity (Butler, 1990), while Foucault's *Discipline and Punishment: the birth of the prison* (2018) is a theoretical foundation for my discussion.

Whether we should have gendered toilets is a complex question because it is multilayered, touching on themes important to human nature, such as the "realness" of gender (Draz, 2022), identity, inequality, persecution, surveillance, tradition, and sexuality. The genderization of spaces is an essential means by which social systems support the organization of gender. They reinforce specific ways of being male or female and maintain pre-existing social roles. Natural forces make one regularly choose between one of two doors with different labels (men/women, gentlemen/ladies, etc.). However, gender minorities are not considered in this binary world. Each visit by a non-conforming person into the most private of gendered public spaces risks a potential confrontation with others' outrage by their perceived "otherness.". How should we solve the problem of gendered spaces for people that are *between the cracks of a dichotomous world* — intersex and transgender people?

In one of the interviews for the project "Shared Spaces" (CCCB, 2015), Judin Butler expressed their support for gender-neutral spaces: "The city has something in common with a prison when it never ends." In the interview, they talk about a public pool with no gender segregation they have been going to: "Men, women, children, abled, disabled or physically challenged—all of us. We are of many ages, we are of many sizes, and we are of many colors. [...] It is something that makes me appreciate the public spaces." According to Butler's idea of gender performativity, there is no ontologically "real" women or men; instead, it is the repetition of gestures, words, bodily movements, societal punishments and awards (Butler, 1990). People are "*menning*" and "*womenning*," following the assigned role. Thus, making the performance a *reality*. The *reality* in Butler's argument is Foucault's idea of *normalization* — "the construction of an idealized norm of conduct" (Foucault, 1978). Demonstrating their argument, Butler points

to drag performances — in which gender is something one can do or practice rather than simply something that anyone is. The core idea here is that there is no "original" self, mirroring Foucault's notion of the absurdness of an idea of *true self* since we all are subject to various powers. Following this reasoning, any spatial segregation based on gender is ontologically groundless since the idea of gender is a social construct that can be altered at any point. Thus, there is no reason for "male" and "female" bathrooms to exist, and we are enabled to abolish them completely by having inclusive bathrooms for all.

One of the possible objections to abolishing gender-segregated public bathrooms and gendered spaces generally can be safety concerns. As Serano puts it: "Instead of trying to 'fictionalize' gender, let us talk about all of the moments in life when gender feels too *real*" (Serano, 2013, emphasis added). In other words, the objection implies that using gender-neutral or gender-segregated public bathrooms is unsafe for both cis and trans people.

Gardner (1995) describes the public harassment of women by men as endemic in our society. However, it is a more severe problem for those whose expression of gender varies from the heteronormative. A person whose gender does not easily fit into a dichotomous box can experience Gender-bashing (K. Namaste, 1996), genderism (Hill, 2003; Browne, 2004), and violent trans-phobia (Feinberg, 1996) triggered by their gender status. Butler (1997) suggests that speech acts must be analyzed within the totality of the experience, while Nielsen (2002, 266) claims that 'public hate speech provides a clear example of how such social hierarchies are constructed and reinforced on a day-to-day basis.

One argument that transgender people do not use toilets in accordance with their gender identity is that it might make other people (presumably cisgender) using the space uncomfortable

(Rios & Resadori, 2015) or even that security, especially in the case of women's toilets, might be compromised.

Therefore, to protect people who identify themselves as neither woman nor man and solve The Bathroom Problem, some proposals with an apparent consensus aim to create a third toilet that is dedicated to transgender people to the detriment of the use of women's (in the case of transgender women) and men's (in the case of transgender men's) toilets.

However, despite the possible use of these toilets by transgender people whose gender identity does confirm the dichotomic system, and as an intervention that proposes to legitimately question the binary division of toilets (without suggesting that transgender people should be forced to use only neutral toilets), this proposal is potentially problematic. Whether it is about safety or privacy, these claims imply that, first, the affections of transgender people are ignored entirely and, second, they are perversely stigmatized by considering them sexually dangerous (Levi & Redman, 2010).

Butler has indirectly responded to the beforementioned solution of the "third gender" bathrooms. In *Bodies that Matter* and *Undoing Gender*, they emphasize that performativity or social construction, more broadly, does not imply the *unrealness* of gender (Butler, 1993; 2004). In an interview in *The Advocate*, Butler clearly supports diverse forms of trans identity, acknowledging the experience some have of gender as an "essential and firmly fixed sense of self." However, Butler's reasoning suggests that proposing that the right way to achieve equality for transgender people is not to separate the group into an "other" category but to treat transgender people the same as the majority and to give everyone access to the bathroom according to their gender identity. However, the problem is not the bathrooms but the binary lens

used for gender and its representation in a spatial arrangement that only cultivates gender performativity. Creating a third group of gender-neutral bathrooms for transgender people only reinforces the claim that such people do not "fit into society."

Safety and privacy when using public restrooms is essential for everyone, including transgender people. Arguments that unilaterally view transgender people's access to restrooms according to their gender identity as a risk to the safety of others imply, even implicitly, that transgender people do not deserve protection by the same standards as the cisgender population. Therefore, Butler's response to another solution to The Bathroom Problem successfully delegitimizes the idea of the third-gender bathroom due to its counterproductivity and the illusion of problem-solving.

I have argued that the relationship between gender and the space in which it manifests itself is dynamic and depends on both spatial context and heteronormativity. Gender matters, but because of its discursive complexity, it matters even more how gender is performed and presented through infrastructure. The experiences of transgender people, as well as of people with gender variations, suggest several important conclusions.

It is time to expand our understanding of gender beyond its social construction to include a separate space where different genders and other differences can manifest. Gender differences exist throughout the human and natural world and have real consequences for people in their daily lives, even when choosing a door for a gendered public restroom, as I discussed in this essay, gender affects how spaces are perceived and what actions are possible, acceptable, or safe. Gender dichotomy, which we can see "from the great strategies of geopolitics to the little tactics of the habitat," is an artifact of patriarchy, and it is time to abandon it, not just for transgender

people but for all of us.

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